

A Study on Online Shopping towards College Students with Special Reference to Kanyakumari District

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Abstract

This study based on the online shopping towards college students in Kanyakumari District. Customer buying is not a mere transfer of an item from the seller to the buyer. Online shopping offers the customer a wide range of products and services they can compare the price quoted by different suppliers and choose the best deal from it. Internet marketing is conceptually different from other marketing channels and internet promotes a one to one communication between the seller and end user with round the clock customer service. The younger generations are now becoming the most valuable consumers in the global market and they play an important role in online shopping. In the past decades, most of the business organizations depend and ran their business with the newer technology particularly focusing on the younger generation. The increasing use of the internet by the younger generation such as Arts and Science students in Kanyakumari District. Based upon this, an empirical study was conducted and the researchers have collected data from 150 Arts and Science Self-financing students of a private university in Vellore by distributing a well-structured questionnaire. The researchers found that the students' spent pocket money in online shopping was above Rs. 10,000 compared to other respondents' with a different slab of pocket money. The researchers found that the attitudes of college students and problems of online shopping are an important independent variable in predicting the preference towards online purchasing.

Keywords: Consumer Behaviour, Online shopping, the Internet, etc.

Introduction of the Study

The Internet is changing the way consumers shop and buy goods and services and has rapidly leveled into a global phenomenon. Many companies have started using the Internet with the aim of cutting marketing costs, thereby reducing the price of their products and services to stay ahead in highly competitive markets. Companies also use the Internet to convey communicates and disseminate information, to sell the product, to take feedback and also to conduct satisfaction surveys with customers. Customers use the Internet not only to buy the product online but also to compare prices, product features and after sale service facilities they will receive if they purchase the product from a particular store. Many experts are optimistic about the prospect of online business. In addition to

the tremendous potential of the E-commerce market, the Internet provides a unique opportunity for companies to more efficiently reach existing and potential customers. Although most of the revenue of online transactions comes from Business -to- Business Commerce, the practitioners of Business-to-Consumer Commerce should not lose confidence. It has been more than a decade since Business-to-Consumer E-Commerce first evolved. Scholars and practitioners of electronic commerce constantly strive to gain an improved insight into consumer behavior in cyberspace. Along with the development of E- retailing, researchers continue to explain E-consumers behavior from different perspectives. Many of their studies have posited new emergent factors or assumptions which are based on the traditional models of consumer behavior, and then examine their validity in the Internet context.

Theoretical Foundation

The Internet has developed into a new distribution channel, and online transactions are rapidly increasing. This has created a need to understand how the consumers perceive online purchasing. Price, Trust, and Convenience were identified as important factors. Price was considered as to be a most important factor for a majority of the students. The internet has created a paradigm shift in the traditional way people shop. A consumer is no longer bound to opening times or specific location. So he can become active at virtually any time any place and purchase the products or services. The internet is relatively a new medium for communication and the information exchange that has present in everyday life. The number of internet user is constantly increasing which is also signifies that online purchasing is increasing. The rapid increasing is explained by the consumer behavior. The internet is considered a mass medium that provides the consumers with purchase characteristics as no other medium. Certain characteristics are making it more convenient for the consumer compared to the traditional way of shopping, such as the ability to any time view and purchase products visualize the needs with products and discuss products with other consumers. Online shopping is the process of consumer go through the when they decide the shop on the internet. The internet has developed into a new distribution channel and the evaluation of this channel. E-commerce has now identified. Using the internet to shop online has become one of the primary reasons to use the internet combined with searching for products and finding the information about them. Therefore the internet develops the companies also use the internet to convey, communicate and disseminate information, to sell the product, to take feedback and also to conduct satisfaction surveys with customers. Customers use the Internet not only to buy the product online but also to compare prices, product features and after sale service facilities they will receive if they purchase the product from a particular store.

Statement of the Problem

Online purchasing of goods, both expensive and cheap is prevalent to a much larger extent in recent years due to convenience, speedy transactions, saving time, attractive sales promotional offers, etc. despite these motivational factors, there involved such as internet user being uncomfortable while giving their credit card number, personal information, etc. which act as deterrent. Online shopping is new, and it is a nascent stage, and there are no hard and fast rules to live by consumers.

Objectives of the Study

The important objectives of the studies are,

- To identify the factors influencing online shopping behavior of college students in Kanyakumari district.
- To analyze the sources of ideas, motivational factors and attitudes among the study unit

Review of Literature

Online Shopping Behaviour - Identifying pre-purchase intentions of consumers is the key to understand why they ultimately do or do not shop from the Web market. One stream of research under online consumer behavior consists of studies that handle the variables influencing these intentions. A compilation of some of the determinants researchers has examined: transaction security, vendor quality, price considerations, information and service quality, system quality, privacy and security risks, trust, shopping enjoyment, the valence of the online shopping experience, and perceived product quality. (Liao and Cheung, 2001; Saeed et al., 2003; Miyazaki and Fernandez, 2001; Chen and Dubinsky, 2003).

The lists of factors having a positive or negative impact on consumers' propensity to shop do not seem to be very different from the considerations encountered in offline environments. However, the sensitivities individuals display for each variable might be very different in online marketplaces. Factors like price sensitivity, importance attributed to brands or the choice set considered in online and offline environment can be significantly different from each other (Andrews and Currim, 2004). Uncertainties about products and shopping processes, the trustworthiness of the online seller, or the convenience and economic utility they wish to derive from electronic shopping determine the costs versus the benefits of this environment for consumers (Teo et al., 2004). Further studies aiming to complete the full set of factors influencing consumers' repurchase intentions are still much awaited.

Research Methodology

This section describes the methodology which includes a collection of data, research design and frame work of analysis.

Primary Data

The primary survey will be collected with the help of well prepared and pre-tested schedule by objectives framed. The data will be collected from sample Self-financing Arts and Science Colleges in Kanyakumari District.

Secondary Data

The data includes a board record, the annual report of the statistical department, theses, books and journals which is related to this research work.

Research Design

“A research design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure.” There are 15 Self-Financed Arts and Science colleges functioning in Kanyakumari District. As per the records of the college calendar 2018-2019, the total no of students are 15000. Due care had been taken while choosing the college students. 1% of the respondents were taken as a sample of the study unit. Thus 150 college students from the Self-financing Colleges are selected in proportionate stratified random sampling method. The list of Self Financing Colleges run by Kanyakumari District is mentioned in table 1.

Table 1 List of Self Finance Colleges in Kanyakumari District

Sl.No	Name of the Colleges	Total Number of Strengths	Proportionate
1	St. Alphonsal Arts and Science College, Mankalakuntu.	800	08
2	Annai Velankanni College, Tholayavattam	1700	17
3	Bethlehem Arts and Science College, Karuingal.	500	05
4	Infant Jesus college for Women, Mulagumoodu.	400	04
5	St. Jerome's College of Arts and Science,	1000	10
6	St. Johns College of Arts and Science, Ammandivilai.	1100	11
7	Malankara Catholic College, Mariagiri.	1200	12
8	Muslim Arts College, Thiruvithancode	1700	17
9	Nanjil College of Arts and Science, Kaliyakkavilai.	700	07
10	Nooral Islam Arts and Science College, Kumarakovil.	1300	13
11	Ruan Arts and Science College, Thadikarankonam.	800	08
12	SivanthiAadhithanar Arts and Science College, Nagercoil.	1300	13
13	St. Theresa College of Arts and Science, Karingal	400	04
14	UdhayaAtrs and Science College, Vellamodi.	1300	13
15	VTM College of Arts and Science, Armani.	800	08
	Total	15000	150

Source: Primary Data

Frame Work

To analyses, the consumer behavior of college students, percentage methods, Chi-square analysis and ranking method are used.

Limitations of the Study

The researcher had the following limitations while conducting the study.

- This study was carried out only among the Self-financing Arts and Science College students.
- The sample size was restricted to 150 due to time constraints.
- The sample was taken at random; therefore the shortcomings of the random sampling may also be present in this study.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The survey results are organized the demographic profile, attitudes and problems faced by the respondents. This section presented the results of data analysis and concluded with expectation

and perception of the College students in Kanyakumari District in TamilNadu regarding online shopping.

Demographic Profile

The data gathered regarding the demographic profile of Self-financing College students in Kanyakumari District constituted such as Age, gender, Educational Qualification, Area of residence and Income. The distribution of students by their profile is given in the table:2

Table 2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variables and Categories	N= 150	Percentage
Age		
17yrs – 19yrs	065	43
20yrs - 22yrs	045	30
Above 22yrs	040	27
Gender		
Male	126	84
Female	024	16
Educational Qualification		
Under Graduate	040	27
Post Graduate	080	53
Research Scholars	030	20
Marital Status		
Married	040	27
Unmarried	110	73
Area of Residence		
Urban	066	44
Rural	048	32
Semi-urban	036	24
Income		
No income but pocket money	047	31
Less than Rs.10000	037	25
Above Rs.10000	066	44

Source: Primary Data

Table:2 exhibits the demographic profile of college students considered for this study. Majority of the respondents are male 126 (84 percent) and were aged between 17yrs- 19yrs. As a result, 110 (73 percent) of respondents are single, and 80 (53per cent) respondents are pursuing Post Graduation degree. Majority of the respondents 66 (44per cent) of the respondents resides in urban areas, and the majority of the respondents 66 (44 percent) of the respondents have over Rs.10000 income. Because these incomes are raised to earn the part-time job like Catering, Centring, etc.

Buying Behaviour

The online shopping process consists of steps similar to those associated with traditional shopping behavior. Online shopping behavior depends upon consumer psychological state regarding making or not making a purchase on the net. Table3 states the buying behavior of online shopping.

Table 3 Buying Behaviour of Online Shopping

Variables and Catagories	N=150	Percentage
Online Shopping Frequency		
Once in a Week	010	07
Once in a Months	085	57
Once in 2 Months	035	23
Once in 6 Months	012	08
Once in a Year	008	05
Frequency of Online Shopping		
Below a Year	024	16
1-2 yrs	082	55
3-5yrs	032	21
Above five yrs	012	08

Source: Primary Data

Table: 3 reveals the shopping frequency with regards to online shopping frequency that majority 85 (57 percent) of the respondents shop products once in a month, 35 (23 percent) of the respondents were shopped products once in 2 months and remaining respondents shop products once in a 6 months, once in a week and once in a year. Table: 3 also shows that higher respondents of online shoppers 82 (55 percent) had been shopping for the products and services online for 1-2 yrs. 32 (21 percent) respondents of online shoppers had been shopping product over the internet for the above five yrs. Only 24 (16 percent) respondents of online shoppers had been shopping below a year. The trend of online shopping present in India, for many years, but it is only in the recent years that this trend of online shopping has been catching up.

Sources of Idea and about Online Shopping Websites

Sources mean to collect the information together with the third parties. It is varied in sample respondents. In this study sources of ideas covered 3 points, i.e., the recommendation of friends, search technics and press and media. These sources are in which kind of motivate and pay the system of cash is also explained in table 4.

Table 4 Sources of Idea and about Online Shopping Websites

Variables and Catagories	N=150	Percentage
Sources of Ideas		
Recommendation of Friends	090	60
Search technics	052	35
Press and Media	008	05
Motivational Factors		
A wide variety of products	075	50
Shop at any time of the day	040	27
No need to travel to the shop	035	23
Mode of Payment		
Cash on Delivery	082	55
Credit /Debit cards	039	26
Bank Transfer	029	19

Source: Primary Data

Table:4 Shows that sources of ideas about online shopping towards college students in Kanyakumari District. Majority 90 (60 percent) of the respondents have an idea about online shopping websites with the recommendation of friends. It also explain majority 75 (50 per cent) of the respondents opines that availability of a wide variety of products is the top motivating factor in online shopping and it can be done at any time of the day and no need to travel to shop.82 (55 percent) respondents availed the facility of cash on delivery of the product and only 39(26 percent) respondents made payment through credit and debit cards and to transfer bank only 29 (19 percent).

Attitudes Towards online Shopping

Table 5 explains the respondent’s attitudes towards online shopping in Self-finance Arts and Science Colleges in Kanyakumari District.

Table 5 Respondents Attitude towards Online Shopping

Sl.No.	Respondents Attitudes	Mean	S.D
1	Online shopping saves time	1.96	.39
2	Shopping can be done at any time	1.71	.51
3	A wide variety of products	1.81	.58
4	Accuracy description of the product	2.10	.90
5	The online shop is as assured as traditional shopping	3.15	1.65
6	Online shopping is risky	3.76	1.56
7	A long time is required for the delivery product	2.24	1.64
8	The necessity of having bank a/c	3.40	1.39
9	Risk of losing privacy	1.95	.53
10	Compared to traditional shopping	3.75	1.63

Source: Primary Data

Datas measured on 5 point scale were strongly agree= 1, Agree= 2, No opinion= 3, Disagree= 4 and Strongly disagree= 5. As per table:5, the average mean attitude score for the statement 1 to 3 and 9 was less than 2, indicating respondents positive response towards this statement. The respondents agree that online shopping saves the time of the customers, it offers a wide variety of products and accurate description about products. The result of the analysis implies that perceived risk internet trait, attitudes traits and convenience are the four dominant factors which influenced the decision of college students in Kanyakumari District to shop online youngsters are technically brilliant, efficient in surfing the net and enjoy internet browsing for fun and information.

Problems Faced by the Respondents While Online Shopping

In any modern business, many problems are raised. In this study of online shopping, behavior raised 5 points of problems faced by the sample respondents.

Table 6 Problems Faced by the Respondents While Online Shopping

S.No	Problems	Respondents	Percentage
1	The product did not arrive at all	15	10
2	Product arrive in damage condition	20	13
3	Wrong product was sent	15	10
4	Not quality goods and service	40	27
5	Others	12	08
6	None of these	48	32
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Above table 6 reveals that majority 40 (27 percent) of the respondents faced the problem is bad quality goods and services in online shopping, 20 (13 percent) of the respondents faced the problem of product arrive in damage condition. 48 (32 percent) of the respondents did not face any of the above problems in online shopping.

Opinions about the Online Shopping

Opinion is the essential role of the online shoppers. These opinions are classified into eight groups. They are payment security, product delivery, personal information privacy warranties, returns policies, convenience, mode payment, time-saving, and attractive offers.

Sl.no	Opinions	Total Score	Rank
1	Payment security	176	6
2	Product Delivery	188	4
3	Personal information privacy	156	8
4	Warranties, return policies	182	5
5	Convenience	215	1
6	Mode of payment	174	7
7	Time-saving	293	2
8	Attractive offers	195	3

Source: Primary Data

Table 7 states that the rank given by the study respondents. The first rank given by the respondents is the convenience in online shopping. Time-saving is the second option by the online shoppers followed by attractive offers and product delivery. The last rank given by the respondents is personal information privacy.

Relationship between Factors Influencing Online Shopping and Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between educational qualification of the college students and factors influencing online shopping.

Table 7 Educational Qualification Regarding as Factors Influencing Online

Factors	Educational Qualification		
	Under Graduates	Post Graduate	Research Scholar
Easy payment	06	03	03
No need of travel	07	09	03
Shop at any time	17	15	09
Access to global brand	09	09	09
A wide variety of product	27	18	06
Total	66	54	30

Source: Primary Data

Table 8 Statistical Test

Chi-Square	Degrees of Freedom	Significant Value	Result
5.0521	12	0.751997	Significant

Source: Primary Data

Table 6 reveals that the relationship between educational qualification of the respondents and factors influencing online shopping. For a majority of the college graduates are under graduates and post graduates a wide variety of the products was the major factor for influencing online shopping.

Table 7 states that at 5% level of significance the chi-square value (.751997) is not significant. Therefore educational qualification of the respondents and factor influencing online shopping are independent.

Findings of the Study

- Majority of the respondents are male 126 (84 percent) and were aged between 17yrs- 19yrs.
- 110 (73 percent) of respondents are single and 80 (53per cent) respondents are pursuing Post Graduation degree.
- Majority of the respondents 66 (44per cent) of the respondents resides in urban areas.
- Majority of the respondents 66 (44 percent) of the respondents have over Rs.10000 income.
- Majority 85 (57 percent) of the respondent's shop products once a month.
- Higher respondents of online shoppers 82 (55 percent) had been shopping for the products and services online for 1-2 yrs.
- Majority 90 (60 percent) of the respondents have an idea about online shopping websites with the recommendation of friends.
- Majority 75(50 percent) of the respondents opines that availability of wide variety of products is the top motivating factor in online shopping and it can be done at any time of the day and no need to travel to shop.
- 82 (55 percent) respondents availed the facility of cash on delivery.
- Majority 40 (27 percent) of the respondents faced the problem is bad quality goods and services in online shopping.
- The first rank given by the respondents is the convenience in online shopping.

Suggestions of the Study

1. The Government should compel the online shopping sites to detail their privacy for conflict resolution.
2. Online security is found to be a major issue influencing the future diffusion of online shopping.
3. Online marketers should use innovative and reachable sales promotional strategies to attract more consumers towards online shopping.

Conclusion

Online shopping becomes increasingly popular for a variety of reasons. The study brought to the Arts and Science College students in Kanyakumari District active, intensive and are expert users of the internet, they have a strong positive perception towards online shopping. Online shopping is becoming increasingly popular for a variety of reason. The study brought to therefore that mini shoppers are young highly educated active, intensive they have a strong positive perception towards online shopping and generally spend a very low amount of online shopping. The findings of this research have confined that the perceived marketing mix and perceived reputation could impact on the consumer's attitude toward adopting online shopping. Through the findings of the online research retailers could of adopting realize online consumer's expectations and the determinants of consumer's behavior. By understanding the key drivers that could impact on line consumers attitudes towards be able to formulate and implement their e-business strongly efficiently and effectively and possess stronger competitively advantage.

The largest driving factor for online vendors should pay more attention to applying the marketing mix of high product quality, lower price, discount, free delivery or gift and do their best to build enhance and maintain their good reputation.

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